

Supplementary Material : Inferring Transcript Phylogenies from Transcript Ortholog Clusters

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S1-Table : Description of the 50 datasets simulated using SimSpliceEvol[6]

Table 1: Description of the 50 datasets simulated using SimSpliceEvol.

Gene Family	# genes	# transcripts	# ortholog groups	# ortho-orthologs	# para-orthologs	# recent paralogs	paralogs
1	6	18	2	52	13	16	72
2	6	12	3	17	13	1	35
3	6	19	3	75	15	6	75
4	5	6	1	6	8	1	0
5	7	9	1	29	5	2	0
6	6	16	2	42	10	5	63
7	6	20	3	40	15	2	133
8	6	7	1	12	8	1	0
9	5	5	1	5	5	0	0
10	6	13	2	25	10	1	42
11	5	12	4	33	0	0	33
12	5	13	3	13	18	1	46
13	5	8	3	19	0	0	9
14	3	4	1	5	0	1	0
15	2	8	4	4	0	0	24
16	5	8	2	19	0	0	9
17	5	17	7	49	0	0	87
18	5	9	3	24	0	0	12
19	2	6	3	3	0	0	12
20	4	30	7	34	14	3	384
21	4	4	1	4	2	0	0
22	5	10	3	32	0	1	12
23	4	7	2	16	0	1	4
24	5	7	2	17	0	0	4
25	5	26	8	186	0	13	126
26	3	26	11	33	0	0	292
27	3	22	9	24	0	3	204
28	2	6	3	3	0	0	12
29	2	10	5	5	0	0	40
30	5	7	2	17	0	0	4
31	5	17	6	74	0	2	60
32	4	17	6	40	0	1	95
33	2	6	3	3	0	0	12
34	2	4	2	2	0	0	4
35	5	7	2	17	0	0	4
36	4	10	4	21	0	0	24
37	4	20	8	43	0	0	147
38	2	10	5	5	0	0	40
39	2	6	3	3	0	0	12
40	5	38	16	121	0	0	582
41	5	7	2	17	0	0	4
42	5	10	2	36	0	6	3
43	4	4	1	4	2	0	0
44	3	7	3	9	0	0	12
45	2	6	3	3	0	0	12
46	2	8	4	4	0	0	24
47	5	8	2	23	0	1	4
48	5	22	7	116	0	6	109
49	3	17	7	23	0	1	112
50	3	3	1	3	0	0	0
Total	210	592	189	1410	138	75	2994

S2-Table : Description of the TAF6 and PAX6 gene families

Table 2: Description of the TAF6 and PAX6 gene families. The isoform structures column is generated by ThorAxe[9] and used as inputs by PhyloSofS[1].

gene family	species	genes	isoform structure	transcripts	IDs
TAF6	Drosophila melanogaster	FBgn0010417	3#0	FBTR0074941	d1
	Danio rerio	ENSDARG00000102998	5#0	ENSDART00000161751	z2
			5#1	ENSDART00000184967	z1
			5#2	ENSDART00000163256	z3
	Mus musculus	ENSMUSG00000036980	6#0	ENSMUST00000048698	m1
				ENSMUST00000110936	m2
	Homo sapiens	ENSG00000106290	7#0	ENST00000687216	h1
				ENST00000689284	h2
				ENST00000686172	h5
				ENST00000687672	h4
				ENST00000687151	h6
				ENST00000690962	h8
				ENST00000440225	h10
ENST00000493322				h9	
PAX6	Mus musculus	ENSMUSG00000027168	6#0	ENSMUST00000111088	m1
			6#1	ENSMUST00000090391	m2
				ENSMUST00000111086	m3
				ENSMUST00000111082	m4
			ENSMUST00000111087	m5	
	Rattus norvegicus	ENSRNOG00000004410	7#1	ENSRNOT00000006302	r1
			7#0	ENSRNOT00000089525	r2
	Homo sapiens	ENSG00000007372	5#2	ENST00000638629	h1
			5#0	ENST00000638914	h2
				ENST00000419022	h3
5#1			ENST00000379109	h4	
Takifugu rubripes	ENSTRUG00000006935	3#0	ENSTRUT00000087876	f1	

S1-Proof : Lemma 5

The procedure $pMinEvoRec(T_1, T_2)$ constitutes a top-down approach and returns the minimum reconciliation cost of SP supertree T obtained by grafting T_1 onto an edge of T_2 . The cost is recursively computed among all the three combinations as shown in Figure [S1-Figure] 1. The optimisation function is described in (4). The recurrence is trivial if T_2 is a leaf. In this case, (4) equals to $cost(I(T_1), I(T_2)) + cost(T_1) + cost(T_2)$ by referring to stop conditions (2) and (3). The stop condition (1) ensures that the recursion will always stop and not continue computations at a level lower than a leaf previously visited. A null score is assigned to avoid affecting the cost of T . Otherwise, if T_2 is not a leaf, for an internal node x in T_2 , the optimization function is recursively looking for the minimum reconciliation cost of T either by placing $I(T_1)$ entirely on the left (resp. on the right) side and then either placing $I(T_{2|x})$ entirely on the left (resp. on the right) side, or by placing $I(T_{2|x_l})$ on the left and $I(T_{2|x_r})$ on the right, or vice versa. At this point, only the cost of $T_2[x]$ ($cost(T_2[x])$) will be recursively recomputed, while the cost of each node $n \in I(T) \setminus I(T_2[x])$ remains unchanged. The minimum reconciliation cost SP supertree of T_1 and T_2 is the minimum between $pMinEvoRec(T_1, T_2)$ and $pMinEvoRec(T_2, T_1)$.

S4-Figure : Comparison with Simulated True Transcript Phylogenies

(a) Distributions of nT distances (using computed transcripts ortholog groups)

(b) Distributions of nT distances (using true transcripts ortholog groups)

(c) Distributions of nQ distances (using computed transcripts ortholog groups)

(d) Distributions of nQ distances (using true transcripts ortholog groups)

Figure 3: (a) Distributions of nT distances between the inferred and the true transcript trees for GIGA and the six versions of our method using the computed ortholog groups[7]. (b) Distributions of nT distances between the inferred and the true transcript trees for the six versions of our method when using the true ortholog groups as input. GIGA is not included because it does not take ortholog groups as input. (c) Distributions of nQ distances between the inferred and the true transcript trees for GIGA and the six versions of our method using the computed ortholog groups[7]. (d) Distributions of nQ distances between the inferred and the true transcript trees for the six versions of our method when using the true ortholog groups as input. GIGA is not included because it does not take ortholog groups as input.

S1-Text : Comparison of transcript phylogenies of families inferred for two case studies on the TAF6 and PAX6 gene families

Transcripts' phylogeny for the PAX6 family

The PAX6 family refers to a group of genes that belong to the paired box (PAX) gene family, specifically focusing on the PAX6 gene. PAX6 is a crucial transcription factor that plays a fundamental role in the development of various tissues and organs, particularly in the embryonic stages, and is subject to heavy alternative splicing transcripts [5]. There are involved in the formation of the eyes, brain, and pancreas. Mutations or dysregulation of the PAX6 genes can lead to various developmental disorders, including the absence of the iris, eye abnormalities and other ocular and neurodevelopmental conditions [2]. Analyzing the evolutionary relationships and phylogenetic history of related PAX6 transcripts will help to better understand their corresponding genes functions and the processes they regulate across different species [3, 8]. To achieve this objective, our focus is on investigating the PAX6 gene family, which comprises gene orthologs maintaining a 1:1 orthology relationship across four species: Human (ENSG00000007372), Mouse (ENSMUSG000000027168), Rat (ENSRNOG00000004410), and Fugu (ENSTRUG000000006935). Using ThorAxe [9], we retrieve 5 transcripts from Human, 5 transcripts from Mouse, 3 transcripts from Rat, and 1 transcript from Fugu. The PAX6 transcript family is described in Table 2 [S2-Table]. The lowest common ancestor of species Human, Mouse, and Rat is a duplication. The presence of this duplication node in the gene tree highlights the dynamic nature of gene evolution, involving events such as gene duplication followed by subsequent divergence or loss.

We applied the PhyloSofS, min_L-MinEvolRec and GIGA methods to analyze the PAX6 gene family as we did for the TAF gene family. The resulting phylogenies offered valuable insights into the impact of alternative splicing and are depicted, respectively, in Figure 4 [S5-Figure] by T_1 , T_2 , and T_3 , positioned from left to right. However,

Figure 4: **[S5-Figure]** (Top) T_1 delineates the transcript phylogeny of the PAX6 family (see details in Table??), as determined through PhyloSofS. Additionally, T_2 illustrates their phylogeny inferred using min_L-MinEvolRec. In T_1 , two trees are depicted within the gene tree, where internal nodes are denoted by rectangles representing ancestral genes. The red and green trees portray the phylogeny of distinct sets of transcripts, with white nodes indicating extant "orphan transcripts" not assigned to any tree. Multiple recent paralogs are condensed into a single leaf node; for example, 6#0 and 7#0 each correspond to one transcript, while 5#1 and 6#1 each represent two transcripts. In T_2 , a red cross at the end of a branch signifies a loss, indicating the termination of a transcript. The colors at the leaves of the phylogeny denote the inferred ortholog groups used for constructing T_2 . Creation events are represented by triangle internal nodes, speciation by black circle internal nodes, and duplication by white circle internal nodes. Colored rectangles below each leaf depict the corresponding structure inferred by PhyloSofS. (Bottom) The figure depicts the guide tree (horizontal left tree) employed in the construction of the transcript tree T_2 (vertical right tree). Four ortholog trees (O_1 , O_2 , O_3 , O_4), originating from input ortholog groups used by the min_L-MinEvolRec method, are visually distinguished by colors at their leaf nodes, corresponding to specific ortholog groups. In this representation, T_2 stands independently at the root, separate from the gene tree, and is linked through the connectivity tree C_{T_2} positioned below. The lengths of the branches in the guide tree are specified, and dotted lines denote additional branches resulting from the merging steps of ortholog trees, labeled with capital letters A, B, and C.

as anticipated, T_3 adheres to the gene tree topology provided at the input, and the presence of polytomies at its leaves fails to accurately represent how transcripts are related, providing limited information about their inferred evolutionary relationships.

T_1 was reconstructed using the third configuration (Creation cost = 3, Loss cost = 3 and Mutation cost = 2). T_1 portrays two sets of conserved transcripts clustered in two trees, represented by the blue and red branches, originating respectively from the ancestral gene 2 and the root (ancestral gene 1). Similar to the analysis of the TAF6 transcripts family, the leaves in T_1 , T_2 , and T_3 depict the transcript isoform structure, grouping distinct transcripts that share a similar structure, i.e., recent paralogous transcripts. In contrast to T_2^* , where colored leaves represent transcripts within the same ortholog groups. Notably, the leaves 5#2 and 6#0 are designated as orphan in T_1 .

The phylogenies T_1 and T_2 exhibit a significant similarity, as the inferred pairwise relations between isoforms remain consistent in both. Furthermore, the ortholog groups effectively discern transcripts within the same tree in T_1 and accurately pinpoint all orphan transcripts by grouping them into unique ortholog groups. Specifically, we identify in \mathcal{D} , depicted in Figure 4 **[S5-Figure]**, four ortholog groups O_1, O_2, O_3, O_4 , representing maximum inclusive wise sets of conserved transcripts. These sets align seamlessly with the groups inferred from the trees (red, blue) in T_2 . Indeed, the ortholog groups O_1 and O_2 in T_2 correspond, respectively, to the red tree and blue tree in T_1 , while O_3 and O_4 are orphans in both. However, T_2 has revealed additional connections among transcripts, particularly within ortholog groups, significantly contributing to the reconstruction of a rooted transcript tree. min_MinEvolRec and PhyloSofS provide similar phylogenies (see Figure 4). More precisely, by truncating the guide tree, the results of min_MinEvolRec align more closely with T_1^3 . In summary, the results of min_MinEvolRec and PhyloSofS are consistent, supporting their accuracy in the absence of ground truth, but min_MinEvolRec is significantly faster than PhyloSofS.

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